

DEVELOPMENT HISTORY OF FOOTBALL ASSOCIATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7491800>

Abstract. The article aims to investigate the history of Football association of Uzbekistan. The article presents some data of development of the association.

Keywords: football, Uzbekistan, Football association, numbers, decrees.

On June 7, 1994, the Football Federation of Uzbekistan became a member of FIFA, and in December of the same year, it became a member of the Asian Football Confederation. The decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 18, 1993 "On measures for the further development of football in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is very important for the development of football in our country. [1].

The decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 17, 1996 "On measures to radically improve the principles of football development and organization in Uzbekistan" was of great importance for the further development of football in Uzbekistan. This decree indicated the future development of football on the basis of clubs and the opening of junior football boarding schools in regional centers in 1996-1997.[1].

In 2002-2003, the players of the youth national team of Uzbekistan achieved great success. In Qatar, after defeating the Thai national team 4:0, Qatar 5:4, and then losing to South Korea 0:2, our players reached the quarter-finals, where they defeated Saudi Arabia 4:0. Uzbek players met with the Japanese national team in the semi-finals. The main time of the intense and intense game ended with a score of 1:1. The Japanese won 4-2 in the 11-meter penalty shoot-out.[2].

The youth national team of Uzbekistan, which took the fourth place, won the opportunity to play among the 16 strongest teams in the world.

The World Championship was held in December 2003 in the UAE. The players of Uzbekistan played a beautiful and well-rounded game, but did not reach the 1/8 finals. However, experts and fans have a high regard for the game of the national team of Uzbekistan. In three matches, they fought against their peers, but with the score of 2:3 against Mali (African champion), 1:2 against Argentina (also world champion), and 0:1 against Spain (European champion). they lost the victory.[3].

In recent years, the national team of Uzbekistan, youth and junior national teams have been participating positively in all World Championships. In 2010, our

national team took an honorable 2nd place in the Asian Youth Championship in Tashkent and qualified for the World Championship. In 2011, our national team took 4th place at the Asian Championship held in Qatar. In 2011, the "Nasaf" team won the Asian Cup for the first time in Uzbekistan. In 2011, he was among the top eight teams at the World Youth Championship held in Mexico. In 2012, our national team took first place in the Asian Youth Championship held in Iran, won the championship and qualified for the World Championship. In 2013, he repeated the result of the World Championship among young people held in Turkey, and entered the top eight.[5].

In 2014, the youth national team of Uzbekistan took part in the World Youth Championship held in New Zealand. The youth national team of Uzbekistan fought in the group stage with the youth national teams of Honduras, Germany, and Fiji to reach the next stage. In the group stage, our representatives defeated the team of Honduras 4:3, the team of Germany 3:0, defeated the team of Fiji 3:0 and qualified for the next stage with the second place. In the semi-finals, the Austrian team competed against the youth national team of Uzbekistan, and in this match, our representatives defeated the Austrian team with a score of 2:0. In the quarter finals, the youth team of Uzbekistan, the African champion, was waiting for the youth national team of Senegal. Our representatives lost 1:0 in a tense match with the African champion.[4].

The youth national team of Uzbekistan, with its participation in the World Championship, became the only team from the Asian continent to leave the group stage, and our national team members Zabihullo Orinbayev, Doston Khamdamov, Eldor Shomurodov played at a high level in defeating the rival teams. they showed These talented players of ours were nominated for the Best Young Player of Asia nomination at the AFC Football of the Year Awards ceremony, and in the end, Doston Khamdamov was named the Best Young Player of Asia in 2014.

In 2015, the Uzbekistan national team performed well in the Asian Cup held in Australia. In the Asian Cup, the national team of Uzbekistan defeated the teams of Saudi Arabia and North Korea in the group stage, lost to the Chinese team and qualified for the 1/8 finals with the second place. In the quarter-finals, they drew with the Korean national team in the main time and lost 2-0 in extra time.

Conclusion. As can be seen that the history of Football association is rich in the games of the association. This claims that football is considered as valuable sport in Uzbekistan. The article shortly presented the development history of association.

References:

1. www.lex.uz
2. <https://web.archive.org/web/20180311061958/>
3. <http://the-uff.com/about/sections/history>
4. Акрамов Р. С верой в искренний футбол. Т.: «Янги аср авлоди», 2012.
5. Futbol. O'quv qo'llanma. 2006. 415

